

Comprehensive Design, Layout, and GDSII Generation of a High-Speed 8-to-3 Priority Encoder for High-Performance Flash ADCs in 90 nm CMOS Technology

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Abstract—Priority encoders are essential in Flash Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs), facilitating the swift and accurate conversion of analog signals to digital outputs. In the ADC architecture, comparators quickly evaluate the input voltage against a set of reference voltages, yielding binary outputs. These outputs are then encoded by priority encoders, efficiently organizing them based on their relative magnitudes to ensure the ADC maintains critical attributes like speed, resolution, and accuracy. This paper discusses about the 8:3 priority encoder which was designed and implemented in cadence 90nm technology.

Keywords: Priority encoder, Layout, LVS, DRC.

I. INTRODUCTION

A priority encoder is an electronic device that receives binary input data and converts them into a reduced number of outputs according to a predetermined priority order, guaranteeing that the input with the highest priority is designated as the output.

The Priority Encoder (PE) is a fundamental logic component used in Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) circuits. One can arrange functions in order of importance, from highest to lowest, to determine the essential ones. The utilization of the Priority Encoder is apparent in the configuration of Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs) and comparators. [1]. An Analogue to Digital Converter (ADC) is a device that converts analog input signals into digital output signals. Among all the available ADCs, the Flash ADC is the fastest. The device is capable of sampling the given analog voltage within a single clock pulse [7].

The high-speed priority encoder is an essential element in the conversion of comparator outputs into a binary-coded signal in a flash Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) [11] shown in fig.1. When an analogue input signal is provided to the ADC, the first step is to compare it with various reference voltages at different stages. This process produces an output pattern known as a "thermometer code." The input to the priority encoder is a binary code composed of ones and zeros.

Fig 1 Block diagram of Flash ADC

Once this thermometer code is given to the priority encoder it processes this thermometer code, determining the position of the most significant "1". It then encodes this position of the MSB into a binary number, which represents the digital equivalent of the analog input signal

The speed of the priority encoder is crucial in High speed Flash ADCs which are utilized in high-speed applications like radar systems, high-frequency communications, and high-definition video processing. The encoders encode the comparator output allows the Flash ADC to achieve high conversion rates.

II. PRIORITY ENCODER

Priority encoder mainly consists of NOT gate and OR gate

Fig .2. Logic diagram of priority encoder

Figure 2 illustrates the logical depiction of an 8-to-3 priority encoder. The diagram depicts the input digital bits, denoted as 'D'0, 'D'1, 'D'2, 'D'3, 'D'4, 'D'5, 'D'6, and 'D'7, which originate from the comparator's output. D7 is assigned the highest priority [12], whereas D0, the bit with the lowest priority, is consistently connected to the ground. The output bits comprise 'Q'0, 'Q'1, and 'Q'2'. 'Q'2' corresponds to the Most Significant Bit (MSB), whereas 'Q'0' corresponds to the Least Significant Bit (LSB).

The first 4-input OR gate takes inputs D1, D3, D5, and D7. Its output, 'Q'0', is logic 1 when any of these inputs (D1, D3, D5, or D7) is logic 1; otherwise, 'Q'0' is logic 0.

The second 4-input OR gate has inputs D2, D3, D6, and D7. The output, 'Q'1', becomes logic 1 if any of these inputs (D2, D3, D6, or D7) is logic 1; otherwise, 'Q'1' is logic 0.

The third 4-input OR gate receives inputs D4, D5, D6, and D7. Its output, 'Q'2', is logic 1 when any of these inputs (D4, D5, D6, or D7) is logic 1; otherwise, 'Q'2' is logic 0.

$$Q2 = D4 + D5 + D6 + D7$$

$$Q1 = D2 + D3 + D6 + D7$$

$$Q0 = D1 + D3 + D5 + D7$$

Table 1 illustrates the truth table of the priority encoder.

Table I. Truth table of Priority Encoder

D7	D6	D5	D4	D3	D2	D1	D0	Q2	Q1	Q0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	1	X	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	1	X	X	0	1	0
0	0	0	0	1	X	X	X	0	1	1
0	0	0	1	X	X	X	X	1	0	0
0	0	1	X	X	X	X	X	1	0	1
0	1	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	0
1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 depicts the diagram and simulated outcome of the NOT gate, while Table 2 exhibits the output of the NOT gate. In order to implement a NOT gate, it is essential to have both a PMOS transistor and an NMOS transistor. The PMOS transistor acts as a pull-up, while the NMOS transistor acts as a pull-down. At high input voltage, the PMOS transistor is in the OFF state, whereas the NMOS transistor is in the ON state. This configuration creates a link to the ground, resulting in a logic 0 output. Conversely, when the input is at a low voltage level, the PMOS transistor is in an operational state, creating a link between the output and VDD, resulting in a logic 1 output. The inverter arrangement is depicted in Figure 4.

Fig .3. Schematic of NOT gate

Fig 4. Simulation of NOT gate

TABLE II. TRUTH TABLE OF NOT GATE

Input	Output
0	1
1	0

Fig .5. Layout of NOT gate

Figures 6 and 7 depict the schematic and digitally-generated depiction of the output of the OR gate. To build an OR gate, a total of six transistors are necessary: four for the NOR gate and two for the NOT gate. The basic principle of the OR gate is that when both inputs are in a low state, the output will also be in a low state. Nevertheless, if there is at least one input in a high state, the output will also be in a high state, as demonstrated in Table 2. Figure 6 depicts the

design of the OR gate, whereas Figure 7 illustrates the simulation of the inputs. Figure 8 depicts the Layout of the OR gate.

Fig .6. Schematic of OR gate

Fig .7. Schematic of OR gate

TABLE III. TRUTH TABLE OF OR GATE

Input A	Input B	Output
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

Fig .8. Layout of OR gate

Fig.9 represents the schematic of the priority encoder with inputs D7-D1 with input signal as shown in Table 4

Table IV. Input Signal Parameters

Input signal	Logic0 voltage	Logic1 voltage	Time period
D7	0 V	2 V	1ns
D6	0 V	2 V	2ns
D5	0 V	2 V	3ns
D4	0 V	2 V	4ns
D3	0 V	2 V	5ns
D2	0 V	2 V	6ns
D1	0 V	2 V	7ns

Fig 9. Schematic of priority encoder

The priority encoder simulation is conducted using three test cases, as illustrated in Table 5. Case i:

Let's examine an 8:3 priority encoder that has inputs 'D1', 'D2', 'D3', 'D4', 'D5', 'D6', and 'D7'. It is important to note that D7 holds the highest priority among these inputs. Based on Figure 10, when D7 is set to a high state, the encoder's output will always be '111', regardless of the states of the lower-priority inputs.

Fig .10. Case i simulation result of priority encoder

Case ii:

In Figure 11, the highest-priority bit, D7, is low. As a result, the next bit in priority, D6, is high. This leads to an output of '110'.

Fig .11. case ii simulation result of priority encoder

Case iii:

In Figure 12, D7, the element with the utmost priority, is low. Similarly, the next highest-priority bit, D6, is low as well. However, D5, the bit that follows in priority, is high, which leads to an output of '101'.

Fig .12. case iii simulation result of priority encoder

Table IV. Test Cases

	D7	D6	D5	D4	D3	D2	D1	D0	Q2	Q1	Q0
Case i	1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1
Case ii	0	1	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	0
Case iii	0	0	1	X	X	X	X	X	1	0	1

The displayed simulations illustrate the output of the priority encoder [13]. After the simulation, the next step is to generate the layout and perform the DRC (Design Rule Check) and LVS (Layout vs. Schematic) rule verification.

Design Rule Check (DRC) is a quality control process used in semiconductor manufacturing and PCB design to validate if a layout adheres to specific rules, such as minimum widths, spacing, layer alignment, via placement, and enclosures. Its purpose is to prevent errors during fabrication and ensure that the design can be manufactured successfully. Figure 13 demonstrates that the arrangement of the priority encoder successfully met the Design Rule Check (DRC) requirements.

Fig .13. DRC of priority encoder

Layout Versus Schematic (LVS) is an essential verification process in semiconductor design that ensures the physical circuit layout accurately corresponds to its schematic. It achieves this by verifying that the components, connections, and their characteristics are correct and consistent with the original design. After successfully passing the Design Rule Check (DRC), the layout must undergo the Layout versus Schematic (LVS) process. Figure 14 illustrates the configuration of a priority encoder that successfully passed the LVS check. Figure 15 depicts the parasitic perspective of the priority encoder.

Fig .14. LVS report of priority encoder

Fig .15. av_extracted of priority encoder

Once the parasitics are obtained, a GDSII file is created, which is then sent to the foundry. Figure 16 displays the GDSII file for an 8-to-3 priority encoder.

IV. CONCLUSION

The 8-to-3 priority encoder, utilising 90nm technology, exhibits a power consumption of 48.44 μ W and a signal delay of 17.95 ps. In the first case, the delay measured was 56.704 nanoseconds, while the suggested design achieved a delay of 17.95 picoseconds, resulting in a reduction of delay by 99.97%. Based on these metrics, it can be concluded that the encoder is both energy-efficient and has a fast response time. This makes it suitable for applications that require high-speed analog-to-digital conversion.

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